

**TURKISH ALPHABET: HISTORICAL ROOTS AND STAGES OF
REFORM**

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Annotation

This article provides a detailed analysis of the historical roots of the Turkish alphabet and the stages of its development through reforms. The research process will cover, on a scientific basis, the views on the alphabet issues, starting from ancient Turkish writing, the Arabic graphics used during the Ottoman period, the reform of the transition to the Latin script carried out during the reign of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, and the first Turkological congress, the Baku Congress, which played an important role in the life of the Turkic peoples. The role of alphabet reforms in language development, literacy levels, and societal modernization is revealed. The article has important theoretical and practical significance in understanding the process of formation of the Turkish alphabet.

Keywords: *alphabet, Kok-Turkic script, newspaper, Turkology Congress, Kopruluzoda, literary language.*

Аннотация

В данной статье представлен подробный анализ исторических корней турецкого алфавита и этапов его развития в ходе реформ. В ходе исследования будут рассмотрены на научной основе взгляды на алфавит, начиная с древнетюркской письменности, заканчивая арабской графикой, использовавшейся в османский период, реформой перехода к латинскому алфавиту, проведенной во время правления Мустафы Кемалья Ататюрка, и

первым тюркологическим конгрессом — Бакинским конгрессом, сыгравшим важную роль в жизни тюркских народов. В статье раскрывается роль реформ алфавита в развитии языка, повышении уровня грамотности и модернизации общества. Статья имеет важное теоретическое и практическое значение для понимания процесса формирования турецкого алфавита.

Ключевые слова: алфавит, кок-тюркское письмо, газета, Конгресс тюркологов, Копрулузода, литературный язык.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada turk alifbosining tarixiy ildizlari hamda uning islohotlar orqali rivojlanish bosqichlari atroflicha tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot jarayonida qadimgi turk yozuvlaridan boshlab, Osmanli davrida qoʻllanilgan arab grafikasi va Mustafo Kamol Otaturk davrida amalga oshirilgan lotin yozuviga oʻtish islohoti va turkiy xalqlar hayotida muhim ahamiyat kasb etgan birinchi turkologik qurultoy – Boku qurultoyidagi alifbo masalalariga oid qarashlar ilmiy asosda yoritiladi. Alifbo islohotlarining til taraqqiyoti, savodxonlik darajasi va jamiyat modernizatsiyasidagi oʻrni ochib beriladi. Maqola turk alifbosining shakllanish jarayonini tushunishda muhim nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit soʻzlar: alifbo, koʻkturk yozuvi, gazeta, Turkologiya qurultoyi, Koʻpruluzoda, adabiy til.

In the 20th century, issues of alphabet and orthography in Turkic languages became an integral part of language reforms, political transformations, and cultural renewal. During this period, alphabet and spelling reforms among Turkic peoples were carried out not only to simplify the linguistic system but also as an important means of shaping national identity and unifying the people.

The frequent changes of alphabets among Turkic peoples can be explained by their wide geographical dispersion, their integration into different spheres of civilization, and their adoption of various religions and cultures. According to current knowledge, the first alphabet used by the Turks for writing the Turkic

language was the Göktürk alphabet. The use of the Uyghur alphabet by the Turks extended from the 8th century to the 17th century, reaching from Eastern Turkestan to the Ottoman court in Istanbul. However, when we look at history, the writing system most widely used by Turkic peoples over the centuries was the Arabic alphabet. This alphabet was the only script used to write historical and modern Turkic dialects from the mid-10th century to the mid-20th century. Even today, this alphabet is used by Uyghurs and Kazakhs living in Eastern Turkestan, as well as by Azerbaijanis and Turkmens living in Iraq and Iran. Today, Turkic languages are written in three different alphabets: Latin, Cyrillic, and Arabic. The last alphabet adopted by the Turks is the Latin alphabet.

In the following centuries, with the strengthening of the field of Turkology, the number of Turkic books published in Europe gradually increased; however, different transcription methods were used for writing Turkish in each of these works.

The idea of adopting the Latin alphabet has been discussed in the Turkish press and intellectual circles since 1910. Intellectuals such as Celal Nuri, Hüseyin Cahit, and Kılıçzade Hakkı, who did not believe that improving the Arabic script would yield the expected benefits, proposed the adoption of Latin letters. This idea, which was put forward during the period of the constitutional monarchy, was implemented by Atatürk on November 1, 1928. Thus, for the first time, the Turkish language acquired a phonetic alphabet in which each phoneme was represented by a separate letter. Today, this alphabet is also used by Turks living in Cyprus and Yugoslavia.

In the Arabic alphabet, which is used in the writing systems of many languages, the Persians added dots to existing letters to represent the sounds ‘ç,’ ‘ş,’ and ‘j,’ while in the 11th century the Turks added letters to represent the sound ‘n’ and the doubled consonant ‘w.’ With minor modifications, the Arabic alphabet was used in Turkic writing until the 19th century, preserving its general

characteristics and traditional form. Although this alphabet, which was most widely adopted by the Turks, did not accurately reflect the sound system of the Turkish language, it was at times regarded as sacred and inseparable from religion. However, with the development of journalism and printing, it began to be seen as a script incompatible with Turkish and was criticized for being difficult to learn and read, and for complicating education.

The initial debates on reforming the Arabic script later evolved into the idea of creating a new alphabet, and discussions increasingly focused on this issue. In 1850, the grammar book *Kavâid-i Osmaniyye*, jointly prepared by Cevdet Efendi and Mehmed Fuad Efendi, addressed for the first time the problems associated with the Arabic script and emphasized the need for a new method of writing. The authors sought to identify sounds present in the Turkic language that could not be represented by Arabic letters.¹ The need to introduce certain modifications to the Arabic script was expressed by Münif Efendi in 1860. Although he proposed two possible approaches, he stated that he preferred the second one: (1) placing vowels and new symbols above and below the letters; (2) writing the letters separately without joining them.² A similar proposal was also put forward by one of the Azerbaijani intellectuals, Mirza Fathali Akhundzadeh. In fact, Akhundzadeh came to Istanbul in 1863 and presented the alphabet project he had prepared to the Grand Vizier.³ Although there were intellectuals of the period who advocated correcting

¹ The Ilkhanid vizier Rashid al-Din likewise criticized the Arabic alphabet; see Rashid al-Din 1939: 5–17.¹⁹ This book was presented to Sultan Abdülmecid at the opening of the *Encümen-i Dâniş* on July 18, 1851, and was published by decision of that institution

² See also: Tansel 1963: 223–249.

³ He wanted the letters to be free of religious associations and considered them part of the ‘*ḥutüt-ı sā’ire-i İslâmiyye.*’ Akhundzadeh proposed removing the dots from Arabic letters and using certain new diacritical marks for writing words. These marks needed to be inserted between letters in order to pronounce words correctly. After returning to Tbilisi, he realized that he could not fully implement his ideas and therefore adopted the idea of using the Latin script. He sent the Latin alphabet project he had prepared to Vizier Ali Pasha, but this attempt was unsuccessful (Ülkütaşir 1973: 19–20).

or modifying the alphabet, Azerbaijani intellectuals were at a more advanced stage in this regard. In 1869, a new draft based on *hurûf-i mukattā* was submitted to newspapers, and Sa'dî's *Gulistān* was printed using this alphabet. Intellectuals such as Münif Efendi, Namık Kemal, Şinasi, Ali Suavi, and later Ebuzziya Tevfik, Yenişehirli Avni, and Nejip Osim clearly demonstrated that they were supporters of reform rather than revolution when it came to the alphabet. Those who opposed abandoning the Arabic alphabet were concerned that the literary and cultural heritage could not be passed on to future generations. Moreover, since the Arabic script was one of the key elements connecting the Ottoman Empire with the Soviet-Turkic world and the broader Islamic world, many did not wish to change it. Ahmad Midhat Efendi, on the one hand, expressed a positive view of applying Armenian and Latin letters to Turkish, but on the other hand, he emphasized that the Arabic letters themselves were not at fault; the issue lay with the education system and its methods.

After 1908, under the conditions of greater freedom, the issue of the alphabet became active again, and supporters of reform were gradually replaced by advocates of a complete revolution. In mass media outlets such as *Tanin*, *İctihad*, and *Hürriyet*, figures like Hüseyin Cahit, Celal Nuri⁴, and Kılıçzade Hakkı⁵ expressed their views in favor of adopting the Latin alphabet. However, since the Arabic script was one of the key elements connecting the Ottoman Empire with the Soviet-Turkic world and the Islamic world, intellectuals such as Zeki Velidi Togan, Nejip Asim Yazıksız, Ayaz Işoqi, and others opposed the Latin alphabet.

⁴ In his work *Tarih-i Tedenniyat-ı Osmaniye-Mukadderat-ı Tarihiye* (1912), Celal Nuri proposed that the Ministry of Education test the Latin alphabet teaching method in a sanjak for one year, and if the population did not achieve literacy within that year, the method should be abandoned (Simshir 1992: 50).

⁵ In 1914, in the journal *Hürriyet-i Fikriye*, published by Kılıçzade Hakkı and his colleagues, a series of articles were printed discussing that reform alone would not be sufficient and that adopting Latin letters was necessary to find a solution.

At the initiative of the Azerbaijani Turks, the movement to adopt Latin letters received the strongest response from Tatar and Kazakh intellectuals. At the Baku Turkology Congress, Kazakh and Tatar intellectuals expressed their support for reforming the alphabet while openly stating that they did not favor adopting the Latin script. In the 1910s, Baytursin applied the Arabic script to the Kazakh Turkic language based on Ismail Gasprinsky's 'Usul-ı Savtiye' method.

In 1908, the Albanians under Ottoman rule switched to the Latin alphabet.⁶

Although discussions on simplifying the language continued between 1923 and 1928, the main focus of the debates was on spelling and the alphabet. In 1923, at the Economic Congress held in İzmir, speeches by Ali Nazmi and his colleagues advocating the adoption of the Latin alphabet met with strong opposition from Kazım Karabekir. The statement by Karabekir was published in the newspaper *Hakimiyet-i Milliye* under the headline 'We Cannot Accept Latin Letters' (March 5, 1923). A year later, Deputy Şükrü Saraçoğlu addressed the Grand National Assembly, noting that the Arabic letters were unsuitable for writing the Turkish language and that articles both opposing and supporting the Latin letters had appeared in succession. Many intellectuals were opposed to adopting the Latin alphabet. Laws regarding the use of international time and the calendar were passed in December 1925 by the Grand National Assembly of Turkey, and in February 1926 the Turkish Civil Code was adopted. The time for writing had now come, but the fears of those opposed to adopting Latin letters were linked to the sudden forgetting of works created over centuries and the severing of spiritual ties with the past.

On February 26–March 5, 1926, at the Baku Turkology Congress, a decision was made that the Latin alphabet should fully correspond to the phonetic structure

⁶ "Shemseddin Sami, an ethnic Albanian, and his brother Abdul Frashëri created a 36-letter Latin alphabet for the Albanians, which was adopted in Southern Albania. This alphabet, known as the Tosk alphabet, began to be widely used in the 1880s

of the Turkic dialects. Following this decision, all Turkic communities abandoned the Arabic script and began writing in the Latin alphabet. About a month later, reporters from the newspaper *Akşam* asked contemporary intellectuals the question, ‘Will the Latin letters be adopted or not?’ Ali Canip (Usul), Muallim Cevdet (İnançalp), Ali Ekrem (Bolayır), Necip Asim (Yazıksız), Avram Galanti, Halil Nimetullah (Öztürk), İbrahim Alaeddin (Gövsa), Veled Çelebi (İzbudak), Hüseyin Suad (Yalçın), İbrahim Necmi (Dilmen), Halid Ziyö (Uşaklıgil), and the Turkologist Zoltan Gomboç opposed the adoption of the Latin alphabet. Only Abdülâ Cevdet and two teachers—Mustafa Hamid, a teacher at Galatasaray Secondary School, and Mustafa Hamit, a former instructor at the Faculty of Oriental Languages at Freiburg University—expressed support for adopting the Latin alphabet (Simshir 1992: 75). The main concern of those who opposed the transition to the Latin alphabet was that it would be impossible to publish thousands of books in the new script, and they feared that the funds invested would be wasted. Two years before the writing revolution, the majority of Turkish intellectuals were against adopting the Latin alphabet.

Written languages using the Latin alphabet, known as Yanalif (the ‘new alphabet’), included the following: Azerbaijani (1925–1939); Tatar and Karachay-Balkar (1927–1939); Kumyk, Nogai, and Altai (1928–1938); Kyrgyz and Kazakh (1928–1940); Crimean Tatar (1929–1938); Khakas (1929–1939); Turkmen (1929–1940); Bashkir (1930–1940); Tuvan (1930–1943); Uyghur (1930–1947); and Gagauz⁷ (1932–1952).

On June 22, 1938, the People’s Commissariat of Education of the RSFSR decided that all Turkic communities in the USSR would use the Cyrillic alphabet⁸.

⁷ Since the Gagauz were outside the Soviet system until 1940, their adoption of the Latin alphabet was not related to the decision made at the Baku Turkology Congress.

⁸ Lenin stated that ‘the Latin alphabet is the starting point of revolutionary movements in the East,’ whereas Stalin argued that ‘the Latin script cannot provide the necessary conditions to bring other peoples closer to the culture of

As a result, a Turkic alphabet of Cyrillic origin replaced the Latin alphabet. Consequently, Yanalif—although it had been widely used in some written languages—was abolished after roughly a decade of use. In 1939, Azerbaijani Turks, Tatars, Yakuts, and Khakas began using Cyrillic; in 1940, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs, Uzbeks, Karakalpaks, and Bashkirs; in 1943, the Tuvans; and in 1957, the Gagauz fully adopted the Cyrillic alphabet.

In conclusion, historical sources indicate that over the course of many centuries, Turkic peoples have used a variety of scripts in different periods and contexts, including the Old Turkic, Sogdian, Uyghur, Manichaean, Brahmi, Tibetan, Assyrian, Arabic, Greek, Armenian, Hebrew, Cyrillic, and Latin alphabets.

In the 20th century, issues of alphabet and orthography in Turkic languages became an important part of language reforms, political changes, and cultural renewal.

The history of the alphabet and orthography among Turkic peoples has gone through several stages. Initially, Turkic peoples adopted various letters and writing systems to develop their written language. In the first stage, ancient Turkic scripts, such as the Kazakh script and runic writing, were widely used.

Later, with the entry into the Muslim world, the Arabic script was adopted as the writing system of the Turkic peoples. During this period, the alphabet and orthography developed in accordance with the Arabic language. At the same time, modifications suitable for Turkic languages and distinctive features within the writing system also emerged.

In the 20th century, among the Turkic peoples, the introduction of the Latin alphabet was accompanied by reforms aimed at developing the language, simplifying the writing system, and adapting it to scientific and technological

the great Russian nation.' Stalin's statement appeared in 1939 in the state's official publication, *Literaturnaya Gazeta*.

advancements. As a result, today Turkic peoples continue to develop their alphabets and orthography in accordance with contemporary needs.

Alphabet and orthography reforms among Turkic peoples have historically been a highly important and complex process, with the primary goals of strengthening national identity, uniting the population, and implementing modern changes in education and culture. These processes were largely linked to political and social transformations, achieving independence, and the establishment of new political systems.

Overall, the stages of development of the alphabet and orthography among Turkic peoples reflect a dynamic and complex historical process, while also encompassing significant reforms aimed at meeting the requirements of modern language.

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